

FAULT DIAGNOSIS : A REVIEW AND ANALYSIS OF VIBRATION DATA AND ITS APPLICATIONS

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10511692

Igor Varejão

UFES, Espirito Santo, igor.varejao@edu.ufes.br .

Alexandre Rodrigues Loureiros

UFES, Espirito Santo, arodrigues.ufes@gmail.com .

Thiago Olivera dos Santos

UFES, Espirito Santo, todosantos@inf.ufes.br,

Flávio Varejão

UFES, Espirito Santo, flavio.varejao@ufes.br.

ABSTRACT

Companies in the industrial sector generally have large investments in modern production equipment, as well as high maintenance costs for these units. Fast and accurate detection of failures and problems in industrial equipment makes a crucial contribution to reducing maintenance costs and improving confidence in production. Fault diagnosis consists of monitoring the operation of equipment in order to identify the occurrence of a failure. With the increase in the number of sensors installed on board in equipment, they have been more used to monitor the status of these equipment and diagnose their failures or malfunctions. Advances in research in the area of Artificial Intelligence, especially in the area of Machine Learning, provide ways to increase the reliability of intelligent fault diagnosis systems and result in a more reliable performance of equipment and industry. This article presents an overview of the vibration data that has been used in several works in the last 30 years, points out a common problem in the use of these data, presents what needs to be done to solve it and how the academic community can contribute to this solution.

Keywords: Fault Diagnosis; Machine Learning; Vibrational Data Analysis; Similarity Bias.

1. Introduction

Intelligent fault diagnosis in industrial equipment consists of applying artificial intelligence techniques to identify the occurrence of faults and the type of fault that occurred.

This is a problem categorized as classification, in which the model is induced to choose one or more classes from a set of possible classes. In general, one of the classes of the problem is the normal class that presents examples of the equipment working without the presence of any failure. The other classes present examples of different types of failures that can occur during equipment operation.

Artificial Intelligence techniques applied in intelligent fault diagnosis typically use data collected by sensors throughout the operating time of industrial equipment. The most commonly used sensors are accelerometers, which capture the magnitude of vibration at a given instant. Data collection can be continuous or occur at regular time intervals. Each measurement can contain data from a single instant in time or a time interval. In general, the temporal sequence in which data is collected is relevant for diagnosing faults. The temporal curves represented by the data sequence indicate patterns of normality and failure.

There is an abundant literature of works that use vibration data for intelligent diagnosis of failures in industrial equipment, which use vibration data collected in laboratory tests or equipment in operation in the field. Artificial Intelligence techniques are used so that the system learns models capable of diagnosing faults by collecting samples of vibration data from equipment in operation. The results reported in these works are generally good or excellent, bringing great hope that these techniques can be applied in everyday industrial life.

This article, however, indicates that the use of these techniques in everyday life is still a long way off. It points out and analyzes in depth a common problem in the works reported in the literature, related to the way data is used and the evaluation methodology used. The paper also proposes a way to eliminate this problem, although this will involve a huge effort from the scientific and industrial community.

In addition to this introduction, this article is organized as follows: Section 2 presents a brief overview of the main Artificial Intelligence techniques used with vibration data in industrial equipment for intelligent fault diagnosis. Section 3 presents the databases most frequently used in these works, summarizing their most relevant characteristics. Section 4 identifies the common problem existing in these works and categorizes them into different subtypes. Section 5 presents our proposal for minimizing these problems. Finally, section 6 presents our conclusions.

2. Fault Diagnosis in Industrial Equipment

Most of the learning techniques used to diagnose faults in industrial equipment are supervised learning, thus requiring that the base examples indicate whether they represent a normal operating condition of the equipment or a condition that represents a specific fault. The type of data from the example base most used in fault diagnosis is the equipment vibration signal.

2.1. Data Domain

The vibration signal is originally extracted as a time series in the time domain, however, to carry out the diagnosis, in practice, transformations are applied to the signal to obtain its spectrum in the frequency domain, which allows the identification of patterns not evident in the time domain.

2.1.1. Time

The temporal signal is obtained by collecting measurements from accelerometer-type sensors located in specific positions on the equipment over a period of time. Each measurement consists of the vibration amplitude at a given instant. The signal extracted in the time domain can be used directly as input to the classifiers, in this case, each measurement corresponds to an input, or as is more common, characteristics of the signal are extracted which serve as input to the classifier. Examples of common characteristics are statistics such as mean amplitude, standard deviation, kurtosis, maximum peak and rms (*root mean square*) of the signal. Figure 1 presents an example of a vibration signal collected in the time domain.

Figure 1 - Vibration signal in the time domain

2.1.2. Frequency

In real-world situations, complex machines with many components generate a varied range of vibrations. Therefore, in engineering practice it is difficult to use time domain signals to analyze the equipment situation. Specialist engineers use signal transformation to the frequency domain, where amplitude peaks can be identified at frequencies typical of defects. The transformation can be easily performed by the Fast Fourier Transform (TRF). Figure 2 shows an example of a signal transformed into the frequency domain of an unbalance defect in centrifugal pumps. Note the peak in the equipment rotation frequency.

Figure 2 - Vibration signal in the frequency domain

2.2. Machine Learning Techniques

Several machine learning techniques have been used in this problem, ranging from feature extraction and selection to various classification algorithms.

2.2.1. Traditional

Traditional classification methods such as k nearest neighbors (WANG, 2016), support vector machines (RAUBER et al., 2021) and decision tree forests (MELLO et al., 2022) have been successfully applied in intelligent diagnosis of failures. Typically, these methods are applied based on statistical characteristics defined with the help of specialized knowledge about the operation of the specific equipment in focus on the problem. Defining these characteristics is the most relevant and laborious step in applying the methods. A broad review of the application of these methods to this problem can be found in (LIU et al., 2018).

2.2.2. Deep Learning

More recently, deep learning techniques (MELLO et al., 2022) have obtained even more promising results in this task. A great advantage of these techniques is to directly extract the relevant characteristics from the raw signal input in the time or frequency domain, eliminating the need to use prior specialized knowledge, which provides greater ability to generalize the application.

Deep learning techniques have been used both as automatic feature extractors, in this case the extracted features are then used as inputs to traditional classifiers, and as classification methods, in this case an additional layer of classification is added so that the feature itself deep neural network can perform classification.

A comprehensive review on the application of these deep learning methods for intelligent fault diagnosis based on vibration signals can be found in (ZHANG et al., 2020).

3. Vibration Data Analysis

Machine learning methods fundamentally depend on the data used as input. Therefore, it is necessary to ensure that the methods used receive quality and numerous data, ensuring sufficient diversity among the data so that the model can abstract the information and learn to generalize the diagnostic task. However, despite the evolution in data acquisition in equipment, the process is still time-consuming and expensive as the machine takes a long time to fail. Therefore, institutions around the world carried out experiments in controlled environments, inducing machine failures or accelerating the process, thus providing the community with *datasets* to train their models. However, each experiment has its particularities that must be

taken into account, such as the type of equipment, rotation frequency, and operating conditions. Given this, below we present the main public *datasets* in the context of industrial equipment divided by degrees of similarity.

3.1. Same Equipment, Same Conditions and Different Conditions

There are *datasets* in which signals from different classes are acquired in the same contexts, that is, the normal and fault signals are acquired from a single piece of equipment using the same conditions, for example, the same rotation frequency and the same load to which the equipment is subjected. The available *dataset* of this type is *Intelligent Maintenance Systems (IMS)*(QIU et al., 2003).

IMS data was collected from 3 *run-to-failure experiments* , each using test equipment consisting of 4 bearings attached to a rod, which was coupled to a motor. Thus, the institute accelerated the bearing degradation process and, in this way, managed to obtain 4 states: normal, inner race failure, outer race failure and pulley failure.

3.2. Same Equipment, Different Conditions

The CWRU (*Case Western Reserve University*) (CWRU, 2021) is probably the most referenced *dataset* in the literature in the context of equipment failure detection. The data provided in this *dataset* was acquired using test equipment consisting of an electric motor in which failures were simulated and tested, including inner race failure, outer race failure and bearing ball failure, as well as the normal state of the machine.

Another *dataset* in this category is the MFPT (*Mechanical Failures Prevention Group*)(MFPT, 2012) *bearing dataset* . The MFPT is made up of 4 bearing states, all obtained with the same rotation frequency, using the same test equipment. The encompassed states are normal bearing conditions, inner race failure and outer race failure.

In addition to these, there is the MAFAULDA (*Machinery Fault Database*) *dataset* (MAFAULDA, 2021) *made available by the SMT (Signals, Multimedia, and Telecommunications Laboratory)* at UFRJ composed of experiments carried out in a machine failure simulator basically composed of bearings connected by a rod, linked to a motor. In this experiment, six different states were simulated: normal state, unbalance failure, vertical and horizontal misalignment and external and internal bearing failure.

3.3. Same Type of Equipment, Different Equipment, Different Conditions

The ESPset *dataset* (*Electrical Submersal Pump data set*) collects vibration data in experiments carried out on submerged centrifugal pumps (BCS), equipment of great importance in the oil industry. The *dataset* contains vibration data from 12 different BCSs, in which a BCS is tested with different rotation frequencies and monitored by 36 accelerometers located at different positions of the BCS. 5 states were identified in the entire *dataset* , the normal signal, sensor/accelerometer failure, misalignment, rubbing and unbalance, totaling 6032 vibration signals.

4. Similarity Bias

An essential part of machine learning is knowing how to evaluate the performance of the algorithm in such a way that the result presented is consistent and performs accordingly when exposed to unseen real-world data. However, many works on intelligent fault diagnosis based on the analysis of vibration signals fail to guarantee this consistency in sampling and their works are sensitive to the so-called **similarity bias** (RAUBER et al., 2021). This occurs because data acquisition is done through time series which are divided into windows to generate different instances for classifier training. Therefore, it should be guaranteed that the division between training and testing does not contain patterns extracted from the same signal in similar periods of time since, if this occurs, the classification task becomes relatively simple. It is important to highlight that, even if the researcher carries out the sampling meticulously trying to avoid similarity bias, there are cases where the *dataset* does not allow the bias to be completely avoided. Given this scenario, there are several degrees of bias that can occur.

4.1. Maximum

When the training and test sets take into account signals from the same equipment tested under the same conditions, the search becomes extremely biased and the similarity bias is at its maximum since, as pointed out above, the classification task becomes trivial given that there is a large dependency between training and test sets. As illustrated in (RAUBER et al., 2021), this case ends up occurring in most machine learning articles applied to fault diagnosis based on vibration data, which routinely report extremely high success rates, approaching 100% accuracy. (RAUBER et al., 2021) carries out an experiment using nested cross-

validation in the CWRU database in which examples from the training and test sets come from the same time series and, as expected, achieve results very close to 100% accuracy. Therefore, the methods used in these articles tend not to work even on equipment used in research but under different conditions.

4.2. Intermediary

Research that uses sampling techniques in which the training set has instances of temporal signals obtained under certain conditions and the test set has instances of temporal signals originating from other conditions reduce the similarity bias, however when the data is obtained from the same equipment and the conditions do not vary significantly, they end up maintaining an intermediate degree of similarity bias. (RAUBER et al., 2021) carried out two other experiments with the CWRU database in which the training and test sets were separated to ensure that the test examples do not come from the same time series used to obtain the training examples .

In the first of them, the difference between the examples of the training and test sets was achieved using different loads on the equipment. In this experiment, load differences did not have much impact on the shape of the time series and the results were close to 95% accuracy, indicating an intermediate, but still high, similarity bias.

In the second experiment, differences were obtained with load variation and failure severity variation. The results dropped significantly, to close to 50% accuracy, showing a significant decline in the performance of the evaluated methods when the bias is reduced.

4.3. Minimum

When the training and testing set is sampled in such a way that the test set data is acquired from equipment different from the equipment used to obtain the training examples, preferably under various conditions of use, the similarity bias is minimal and, in this case, the results obtained are more likely to be generalizable.

5. Integration and Expansion of Databases

Even if care is taken to minimize similarity bias, the ability to generalize the results remains questionable, since, in practice, real conditions are quite varied and normally different from the conditions used in experiments.

One way to move forward in solving this problem would be to set up a large database composed of the integration of public databases into a single database used for training and testing the classifiers. Classifiers with good results would have a greater possibility of generalization considering that the data set used for training is much more varied and distinct from the set used in testing. Currently, we have invested in creating this database and evaluating the impact of using it together with intelligent fault diagnosis methods.

A more challenging and promising project in this direction would be to create an integrated and expanded database collecting signals under different conditions from different types of equipment for various fault diagnosis tasks, such as the ImageNet *dataset* (DENG et al., 2009) from the computer vision. This way, there would be enough data for the division between training and testing to be made without any similarity *bias*. This is a challenging project that will require a great effort from the scientific and industrial community.

6. Final Considerations

At the time of publication of this article, there is no public *dataset* that uses different types of equipment with different equipment to acquire vibration data. Therefore, it becomes a necessary effort to disseminate an integrated *dataset* of vibration data to the academic community, as proposed in this article, so that future work can be carried out so that sampling can be set up so that various types of equipment are used. and that, in the test set, there are types of equipment not found in the training set. That said, there would be no similarity *bias* in the research and, therefore, if an article reports good results satisfying these conditions, it would indicate that the use of these techniques on a daily basis is quite viable.

References

CWRU. **Case Western Reserve University Bearing Dataset Center**. Available at: <<https://engineering.case.edu/bearingdatacenter>>. Accessed on: 17 September. 2022.

DENG, J. et al. **ImageNet: A large-scale hierarchical image database** . 2009 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition. **Proceedings ...** In: 2009 IEEE CONFERENCE ON COMPUTER VISION AND PATTERN RECOGNITION. Jun. 2009.

LIU, R. et al. Artificial intelligence for fault diagnosis of rotating machinery: A review. **Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing** , vol. 108, p. 33–47, 1 Aug. 2018.

MAFAULDA. **Machinery Fault Database** . Available at:<http://www02.smt.ufrj.br/~offshore/mfs/page_01.html#SEC1>. Accessed on: 17 September. 2022.

MELLO, LHS et al. Ensemble of metric learners for improving electrical submersible pump fault diagnosis. **Journal of Petroleum Science and Engineering** , vol. 218, p. 110875, 1 Nov. 2022.

MFPT. **Fault Data Sets - Society For Machinery Failure Prevention Technology** . Available at: <<https://www.mfpt.org/fault-data-sets/>>. Accessed on: 17 September. 2022.

QIU, H. et al. Robust performance degradation assessment methods for enhanced rolling element bearing prognostics. **Advanced Engineering Informatics** , Intelligent Maintenance Systems. v. 17, no. 3, p. 127–140, 1 Jul. 2003.

RAUBER, TW et al. An experimental methodology to evaluate machine learning methods for fault diagnosis based on vibration signals. **Expert Systems with Applications** , vol. 167, p. 114022, 1 Apr. 2021.

WANG, D. K-nearest neighbors based methods for identification of different gear crack levels under different motor speeds and loads: Revisited. **Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing** , vol. 70–71, p. 201–208, 1 Mar. 2016.

ZHANG, S. et al. Deep Learning Algorithms for Bearing Fault Diagnostics—A Comprehensive Review. **IEEE Access** , v. 8, p. 29857–29881, 2020.